

Blending of three-dimensional geometric model shapes

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Jul 30, 2021

Revised Apr 14, 2022

Accepted May 25, 2022

Keywords:

3D reconstruction

Image-based modeling

Part blending

Part matching

Shape creation

ABSTRACT

Three-dimensional (3D) geometric model shapes blending method can create various in-between models from two inputs of models shapes. Though, many blended shapes are implausible due to different inputs of model type, inappropriate matching-parts, improper parts-segmentation, and non-tally number of segmentation parts. are crucial and should be taken into account. The objective of this paper is to study the strengths and weaknesses of some prominent shapes blending methods and the 3D reconstruction methods. An interpolated shape blending program using the Laplacian-based contraction and Slinky-based segmentation method is developed to illustrate the critical problems arise in the shape blending process. Output results are to be compared with some prominent existing methods and one will observe the potential research direction in the blending research work.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensional (3D) modeling is getting more and more important nowadays especially in the games and movies industries to meet the audiences' visual excitement. The most common modeling method is through using modeling software. The frequently used window-based modeling software are 3D Blender, Wings 3D, Meshmixer, FreeCAD, 3D Slash, and Sculptiris. These open-source software however, are more suitable for the beginners, except 3D Blender which can create more advance stuff. Other advance but not free modeling software are 3D Maya, Houdini 17.5, Cinema 4D R20, Autodesk 3ds Max, and Lightwave 3D. They are more suitable for creating advance and complex graphic models and special effects. The software employ modeling techniques like spline/non-uniform rational B-spline (NURBS) modeling, subdivision/box modeling, contour modeling, digital sculpting and surface modeling [1], to speedily construct high quality of 3D models. In general, using the software to create 3D models still requires time, experiences and skills.

Another modeling technique is the image-based modeling which input two-dimensional (2D) or Two-and-a-half-dimensional (2.5D) static images to construct a 3D model. The more input of images, the more refined detail of the model would be generated. However, the processing time to construct the geometric details from the images and the combination of the piecewise detail from each image is undoubtedly will be increasing. This has not covered the processing time for calibrating the image sequences for the purpose of denoising and improving the quality of the image. Nevertheless, the latest research work is heading towards the un-calibrated work [2] and the minimal use of number of images to speed up the construction of the 3D models. Constructing a 3D model from the scratch is a pain [3] to many modelers in games and entertainment industries. It is an agony to come up with a new model design for the fresh visual excitement. One of the solutions to this problem is by using the model blending method. It blends (or combines) two or more input of 3D models and outputs a new design of 3D model automatically.

Next section, we will review some prominent blending methods. In section 3, we will discuss some 3D reconstruction techniques. Although processing the images is time-taking, this research area is getting more attention because if the number of images to be used reduces, it can shorten the processing time very much. In section 4, we will demonstrate a simple blending work and some results for visual understanding. Section 5 will discuss the future direction of the blending research work.

2. 3D BLENDING METHODS

Model shape blending and model shape morphing are two frequently overlapped terminologies used in many literatures. Technically, shape blending combines two or more model shapes to form a new shape. The new shape is expected to be the intermediate shape of all the inputs. For instance, in Figure 1, the long, slim and straight magenta object (left) is blended with a short, curvature cyan object (middle). This produces an average height, slight-curvature blue object (right).

Figure 1. Two model shapes are blended to form a new shape

Meanwhile, shape morphing is a transition of shapes from one source of model to a targeted model. The result will be a sequential of models. The midway transitioned model may be similar to the blended model shape. Though, this method can only transact two model shapes at one moment. Unlike shape blending method, it not only can combine more than two model shapes at one moment, the resultant shape may completely be different from the input shapes. Therefore, shape blending method is more preferred for creating new ideas in the design world; whereas shape morphing is more preferred for creating animation in the interactive world. In this section, we will review and analyze on a few remarkable shape blending methods.

Jain *et al.* [4] analyzed each feature shape, its adjacency features and the symmetry features before combining parts to form an object. Their system performed hierarchical pairing between the shapes, combining parts which have almost the same positional information in the nodes of the hierarchy. The pairing is interpolated from coarse-to-fine parts and subsequently swaps and combines to produce new models. Their method does not involve any manual intervention. Though, the output is very much depended on the accuracy of the segmentation of the parts. Besides that, their algorithm needs to have equal matching parts. If one input has very little parts and the other input has a lot of parts, then, the final output will result to very little exchange of parts or might produce unpleasant models.

Alhashim *et al.* [5] and Wu *et al.* [6] applied structural-based concept to blend two topology-varying input model shapes. Their blended result comprised of the basic structure (or functional) of the input models. When blending two input chairs, the output should remain to be a chair-like model. To achieve that, they shrank the input models into a skeletal representation. Then, each skeletal part was identified and made corresponded between the source and target models semi-automatically (user input was involved). Blending process was executed via topological events in different orders. The preserved structure would filter off implausible in-between graph. The remaining unfiltered in-between structural graphs are mesh-reconstructed through an inverse mapping from the skeletal representation to the surfaces model. The method still requires a few improvements such as accurate segmentation for meaningful parts, proper parts corresponding for creating a logical functional shape, and the input model shapes are limited to tubular and sheet-like parts (non-complex shapes).

Huang *et al.* [7] interestingly blended two models to produce new stylized models. They inputted a base model which was purely a non-textured 3D geometric model, and a style model which was a textured 3D geometric model. The base model would dominate the basic shape of the new model. For instance, input a “stylized” cow model and a “base” cup model will result to a cow-like cup of shape. For blending the two inputs, Huang *et al.* constructed a tree-growing data structure to filter off the implausible parts-combined models based on six different aspects. Then, based on the topology merging graphs, they applied soft matching to combine the corresponding parts. Their proposed method can blend any models from different

categories such as to blend a life object with a lifeless object, which is very different from previous works. Nevertheless, their method is complex and involves human intervention.

Ong *et al.* [8] applied slinky-based segmentation method to auto-segment input models into functional parts. Both models' parts were scaled, oriented and matched accordingly. Then, swapping of parts was executed from one model to another model. Their method is simple but both models need to be equaled in number of parts. Also, their input models can only deal with the same object.

Hua *et al.* [9] employed Hausdorff distance method to match parts from two input models. They proposed two approaches to blend the matched parts. The first approach simply interpolates the vertices and faces from one part to the corresponding part for creating in-between parts. The second approach parameterized the part-pair spherically to a combined mesh and interpolate the vertex in the combined mesh for in-between parts. The created variations of models are of the plausible shape and with fine functionality. Though, the approaches require same category of objects for the blending such as to blend a round table with a square table, and both input models must share the same number of segmented parts.

3. 3D RECONSTRUCTION

3D reconstruction can be heavily device dependent or alternatively, a less costly approach which rely more on economic data acquisition and data processing techniques. The former approach usually requires investment on expensive devices or sensors to achieve high accuracy while latter approach invites opportunities for improvements in processing algorithms to obtain acceptable results. Research can range from investigating affordable setups and instrument for data acquisition to designing frameworks to filter/manage/process data and reconstruct 3D surface. The discussion in this section will be categorized to modelling objects, human face and body/pose, and environment like room, terrain or building.

3.1. Modeling objects

With the rapid advancements in camera technology and computer processors, image-based modeling (IBM) is gaining momentum. Rather than investing on costly devices like coordinate measuring machines (CMM) or laser scanners to achieve high accuracy, researchers invest their effort in investigating approaches to perform 3D reconstruction using more affordable and easily available hardware like consumer digital cameras, webcams or even build in cameras on mobile phones. Shujaa and Abdulmajeed [10] applied neural network (NN) technique for the depth estimation process.

Some researchers use red, green and blue color (RGB-D) sensors like Microsoft Kinect for 3D reconstructions, where Kinect v1 and v2 each uses structured light (SL) and time of flight (ToF). The former deducts the distance based on the infrared (IR) pattern's distortion on the object's surface while the latter captures the time used for light to travel to the object surface and reflected to the receiver. Kinect v1 is suitable for indoors only as it does not perform well under bright sunlight [11] and the accuracy decreases exponentially with increasing distance [12]. Yang *et al.* [13], Kinect has few advantages, including the ability to perform well under low light conditions, to resolve pose silhouette ambiguities, and is color and texture invariant.

According to Durou *et al.* [14], 3D reconstruction techniques from digital cameras can be classified as either geometric or photometric and the number of images required is either single or multiple, as show in Table 1. Geometric shape-from-X techniques identify features from the images, while photometric shape-from-X techniques analyze the quantity of light received in each photosite of the camera's sensor.

Table 1. Main shape-from-X techniques [14]

	Geometric techniques	Photometric techniques
Single image	Structured light	Shape-from-shading (SfS)
	Shape-from-shadows	
	Shape-from-contours	
	Shape-from-texture	
	Shape-from-template	
Multi-images	Structure-from-motion	Photometric stereo Shape-from-polarisation (SfP)
	Stereopsis	
	Shape-from-silhouettes	
	Shape-from-focus	

Boora *et al.* [2] attempted to perform 3D reconstruction with images obtained from mobile phones. Tracking was done with Kanade-Lucas-Tomasi (KLT) feature tracking algorithm and then the feature points were projected to approximate the 3D world point. Nevertheless, the authors were unable to obtain the actual

size of object. On the other hand, Ng [15] performed depth value approximation with Lucas Kanade optical flow and trigonometry. Images of 640x480 pixels were taken using webcam and the actual size of objects were able to be approximated in a calibrated environment.

Yamada and Kimura [16] evaluated the performance of two famous keypoint detection/feature descriptor used for 3D reconstruction, namely scale invariant feature transform (SIFT) [17] and accelerated-KAZE (AKAZE) [18]. They found that AKAZE performed slightly better than SIFT, but sufficient 3D reconstruction were not obtained if only the descriptors were used separately, and hence, they proposed the combination of both to obtain better 3D reconstruction results.

Most of the times, when performing IBM, problems like hole or noise will occur. Holes might be due to lack of features to track, or part(s) of the subject was occluded. Awang *et al.* [19] proposed enhanced advancing front mesh (EAFM) method to overcome the problem of finding new point in a hole of missing area. The enhanced method was an improvement of the original advanced front method (AFM) and their results was able to introduce more points in a hole to represent better features of the object. On the other hand, problem will occur in active systems like laser scanner when trying to obtain 3D points of surfaces which do not reflect light, such as black or transparent surfaces.

3.2. Modeling human

Human face modeling with Microsoft Kinect has also lots of room for research, especially after the release of Kinect v2 in 2014. Wasenmüller and Stricker [12] have evaluated that Kinect v2 outperformed Kinect v1 in terms of usage in 3D reconstruction, simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) or visual odometry. Human reconstruction using Kinect basically can be either focusing on the face only [20], or on the body/pose [21]. According to Zheng *et al.* [22], research findings in image-based reconstruction of a human body can be useful for virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) content creation. They proposed a deep-learning based framework to reconstruct 3D human model using a single image.

3.3. Modeling environment

When talking about indoor reconstructions, 3D room can be obtained either using Microsoft Kinect [23]-[25] or image [26]. To overcome the problem of visual attributes' limitations such as transparent and highly reflective objects such as windows or mirrors, Kim *et al.* [27] proposed the combined usage of audio-visual data to complement the visual limitations. They captured the environment with 360° cameras and recorded acoustic room impulse responses (RIRs) with a loudspeaker and compact microphone array. Depth information of the scene is recovered by stereo matching from the captured images and estimation of major acoustic reflector locations from the sound.

Meanwhile, for modeling large outdoor areas such as buildings or terrains, light detection and ranging (LiDAR) will be used. Its instrument fires up to 150,000 pulses per second of laser light at a surface. Like ToF cameras, the distance is deducted by the amount of time it takes for each pulse to bounce back to the instrument. Generally, LiDAR can be categorized into airborne LiDAR and ground-based LiDAR. Airborne LiDAR can provide higher levels of detail and hence is a more popular source of terrain mapping [28]. Their usages include forestry management and planning, oil and gas exploration, archaeology and many more. Meanwhile, ground-based LiDAR is used for more localized reconstructions, such as building reconstruction and navigation for autonomous vehicles. Yang and Fan [29] used 3D LiDAR points to reconstruct buildings. The filtered data is processed using random sample consensus (RANSAC) algorithm and region-growing algorithm for plane detection. Finally, the authors reconstruct the 3D building using the four corner points of the plane. On the other hand, Ashraf *et al.* [30] implemented synthetic aperture radar (SAR) for reconstruction by processing of radar echoes based on adaptive orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP) compression sensing.

On the other hand, building and terrain modeling can also be performed using ariel images. Ban *et al.* [31] utilize height map generated from a satellite image and then perform refinement of 3D mesh to remove stair shape on the side of buildings. Meanwhile, Sugiura *et al.* [32] proposed high quality 3D surface reconstruction, specially for man-made structures, as triangular meshes by combining 3D line segments with the point cloud obtained from Structure from motion (SfM).

4. ANALYSIS ON THE POTENTIAL RESEARCH PROBLEMS IN 3D BLENDING WORK

This section will discuss the potential problems while working on the 3D blending research work. The examples given in this section are our implemented interpolation of geometric model blending using the Laplacian-based contraction and Slinky-based segmentation method [33]-[34]. Due to limited paper length, readers may refer to the cited papers for more information on the contraction and segmentation methods. The following will focus only on the blended-related output results.

Most of the blending techniques require input objects to be accurately segmented for functional parts [35]-[36], so that their appearance is plausible and meaningful for latter blending activity. Figure 2 exhibits the quality of the model segmentation. Figure 2(a) shows two dogs, which the (left) dog is poorly segmented and the (right) dog is appropriately segmented. The poor segmented model will lead to many implausible parts. The over-segmented parts will result to open mesh which will create a lot of unwanted holes. Figure 2(b) shows the comparison of our proposed method to the existing seven prominent methods. The details of the seven methods are discussed in [33]. Accurate segmentation plays a very crucial role to ensure the correctness at the preliminary stage. Otherwise, the following processes and output results will all be deviated.

Part-matching is another crucial criterion to take into account. Many existing blending methods (except the method proposed by Huang *et al.* [7]) require the input models to be the similar type and same number of segmented parts. Figure 3 exhibits the input model type. Figure 3(a) shows the same type and same number of segmented parts. If both the models do not share the same number of segmented parts (e.g. Figure 3(b)), then, the model with more parts shall merge some of the parts. This stage will require some intelligences to choose the most suitable parts to merge. For Figure 3(b) right hand model, the best choice is merging the palm with the wrist, and not merging the palm with any finger. This can be determined via skeleton analysis which is not within the scope of our discussion here.

Figure 2. Quality of the model segmentation (a) poor-segmented left-dog model and well-segmented right-dog model and (b) comparison between our proposed method with seven existing prominent methods

Figure 3. Input model type (a) both input models are of same type and same number of segmented parts and (b) both models are of same type but with different number of segmented parts

Part-blending process or part-swapping process does not usually produce obvious weird result. They are simply interpolated (or exchange) from one source part to the targeted part. Figure 4 exhibits the blended result. Figure 4(a) shows two legs of the chairs are blended. The source leg is thick and slanted; the target leg is slim and straight. The blended leg is less thick and is slightly slanted. The result is plausible, but a straighter leg is preferred for the stability purpose. Figure 4(b) shows a blended oval/diamond from a cuboid and a sphere/diamond. Technically, the orientation of the target part should be preserved. Only the size or the shape of the part is modifiable.

The last critical activity of the blending process is to ensure the blended part attach properly or realistically to the original model. In Figure 5, it shows that the blended leg is not properly attached to the seat of a chair. Though, this is not a difficult problem. One can simply find the centric coordinates of the seat-hole and the blended-leg-hole, and then translate and orientate the blended-leg hole to merge with the Seat-hole.

Figure 4. Blended result (a) source part (left), target part (middle), blended leg (right) and (b) source part (left), target part (middle), blended oval/diamond (right)

Figure 5. Blended leg is not properly attached to the model (bottom view)

5. FUTURE DIRECTION OF 3D BLENDING

Many proposed blending methods are either semi-automatic or involve some human intervention to pair the functional parts. This has not included the human intervention in segmenting the models. At present, computer is still unable to imitate human brain to determine the orientation of various models, so that it can properly align and match the parts accurately. Many existing methods applied structured link among the segmented parts and tried blending the parts hoping to form a logical model. Deep learning approach is one of the potential areas for solving this problem. So far, not many deep learning approaches have been applied in three-dimensional field. This may deal to the already complicated neural network in two-dimensional field. The extension may exponentially burden the memory and the computation performance.

Blending method is gradually widely applied to many industrials such as manufacturing industry, civil construction industry, automobile industry, and entertainment industry. by blending existing products/models for different products/models design. The input models are no longer the simple model meshes and/or small object size, but could be more than billion points of coordinates and/or huge and complex 3D screen. The used of graphics processing unit (GPU) may be insufficient to handle its bottleneck.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper reviews a few prominent 3D blending methods and 3D reconstruction methods for creating new or in-between models. It has also discussed some potential blending problems to solve at present time and some future direction of the model blending activities in the industries. A blending program is developed to illustrate the results and the potential problems. The 3D segmented result is to be compared with some existing prominent methods. Some blended results are demonstrated using the primitive models.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The work is supported by Universiti Putra Malaysia under Geran Putra-Insentif Pensyarah Muda (GP-IPM/2018/9621300).

REFERENCES

- [1] J. W. Tangelder, and R. C. Velkamp, "A survey of content-based 3D shape retrieval methods," *Multimedia tools and applications*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 441-471, 2008, doi: 10.1007/s11042-007-0181-0
- [2] S. Boora, B. C. Sahu, and Di. Patra, "3D image reconstruction from multiview images," in *8th International Conference on Computing, Communications and Networking Technologies, ICCCNT 2017*, Jul. 2017, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/ICCCNT.2017.8204120.

- [3] Y. Sahillioğlu, "Recent advances in shape correspondence," *Visual Computer*, vol. 36, no. 8, pp. 1705–1721, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s00371-019-01760-0.
- [4] A. Jain, T. Thormählen, T. Ritschel, and H.-P. Seidel, "Exploring shape variations by 3D-model decomposition and part-based recombination," *Computer Graphics Forum*, vol. 31, no. 2pt3, pp. 631–640, May 2012, doi: 10.1111/j.1467-8659.2012.03042.x.
- [5] I. Alhashim, H. Li, K. Xu, J. Cao, R. Ma, and H. Zhang, "Topology-varying 3D shape creation via structural blending," *ACM Transactions on Graphics*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 1–10, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.1145/2601097.2601102.
- [6] Z. Wu, X. Chen, L. Yu, A. Telea, and J. Kosinka, "Co-skeletons: Consistent curve skeletons for shape families," *Computers and Graphics (Pergamon)*, vol. 90, pp. 62–72, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.cag.2020.05.006.
- [7] Y. J. Huang, W. C. Lin, I. C. Yeh, and T. Y. Lee, "Geometric and textural blending for 3D model stylization," *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 1114–1126, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TVCG.2017.2657751.
- [8] K. Ong, K. W. Ng, and Y. J. Yoong, "3D shape blending: parts swapping," in *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, Nov. 2019, pp. 117–121, doi: 10.1145/3372422.3372445.
- [9] S. Hua, A. Xiong, and M. Bai, "Matched part-pair blending for 3D shape creation," *Computer-Aided Design and Applications*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 193–205, Feb. 2017, doi: 10.1080/16864360.2016.1223431.
- [10] M. I. Shujaa and A. A. Abdulmajeed, "Implementing bezier surface interpolation and N.N in shape reconstruction and depth estimation of a 2D image," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 1609–1616, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v16.i3.pp1609-1616.
- [11] D. Pagliari, L. Pinto, M. Reguzzoni, and L. Rossi, "Integration of kinect and low-cost gnss for outdoor navigation," *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, vol. XLI-B5, pp. 565–572, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.5194/isprs-archives-xli-b5-565-2016.
- [12] O. Wasenmüller and D. Stricker, "Comparison of kinect v1 and v2 depth images in terms of accuracy and precision," in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 10117 LNCS, 2017, pp. 34–45, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-54427-4_3.
- [13] L. Yang, L. Zhang, H. Dong, A. Alelaiwi, and A. El Saddik, "Evaluating and improving the depth accuracy of Kinect for Windows v2," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 15, no. 8, pp. 4275–4285, Aug. 2015, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2015.2416651.
- [14] J. D. Durou, M. Falcone, Y. Quéau, and S. Tozza, "A comprehensive introduction to photometric 3D-reconstruction," in *Advances in Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2020, pp. 1–29, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-51866-0_1.
- [15] S. B. Ng, "Depth value approximation of 2D complex-shape objects for 3D modelling using optical flow and trigonometry," Doctoral thesis, Universiti Putra Malaysia, 2018.
- [16] K. Yamada and A. Kimura, "A performance evaluation of keypoints detection methods SIFT and AKAZE for 3D reconstruction," in *2018 International Workshop on Advanced Image Technology, IWAIT 2018*, Jan. 2018, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/IWAIT.2018.8369647.
- [17] D. G. Lowe, "Distinctive image features from scale-invariant keypoints," *International Journal of Computer Vision*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 91–110, Nov. 2004, doi: 10.1023/B:VISI.0000029664.99615.94.
- [18] P. F. Alcantarilla, J. Nuevo, and A. Bartoli, "Fast explicit diffusion for accelerated features in nonlinear scale spaces," in *BMVC 2013 - Electronic Proceedings of the British Machine Vision Conference 2013*, 2013, pp. 13.1-13.11, doi: 10.5244/C.27.13.
- [19] N. Awang, R. W. Rahmat, N. S. Beng, A. Jaafar, and P. S. Sulaiman, "Filling simple holes by using enhanced advancing front mesh method (EAFM): Application to a real object," *Civil Engineering and Architecture*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 251–261, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.13189/cea.2019.070503.
- [20] R. Siv, I. Ardiyanto, and R. Hartanto, "3D human face reconstruction using depth sensor of Kinect 2," in *2018 International Conference on Information and Communications Technology, ICOIACT 2018*, Mar. 2018, vol. 2018-January, pp. 355–359, doi: 10.1109/ICOIACT.2018.8350702.
- [21] G. Chen, J. Li, B. Wang, J. Zeng, G. Lu, and D. Zhang, "Reconstructing 3D human models with a Kinect," *Computer Animation and Virtual Worlds*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 72–85, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1002/cav.1632.
- [22] Z. Zheng, T. Yu, Y. Wei, Q. Dai, and Y. Liu, "DeepHuman: 3D Human Reconstruction from a single image," in *2019 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, Oct. 2019, vol. 2019-October, pp. 7738–7748, doi: 10.1109/ICCV.2019.00783.
- [23] D. Wolters, "Automatic 3D reconstruction of indoor Manhattan world scenes using kinect depth data," in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 8753, 2014, pp. 715–721.
- [24] J.-W. Li, D.-F. Zheng, Z.-H. Guan, C.-Y. Chen, X.-W. Jiang, and X.-H. Zhang, "Indoor 3D scene reconstruction for mobile robots using Microsoft kinect sensor," in *2016 35th Chinese Control Conference (CCC)*, Jul. 2016, pp. 6324–6328, doi: 10.1109/ChiCC.2016.7554350.
- [25] E. Mangina, C. Gannon, and E. O'Keefe, "Reconstructing a 3D Room from a Kinect Carrying UAV," in *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, vol. 1035, 2019, pp. 74–87, doi: 10.1007/978-981-13-9181-1_7.
- [26] H. Yang and H. Zhang, "Efficient 3D room shape recovery from a single panorama," in *Proceedings of the IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Jun. 2016, vol. 2016-December, pp. 5422–5430, doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2016.585.
- [27] H. Kim, L. Remaggi, P. J. Jackson, F. M. Fazi, and A. Hilton, "3D room geometry reconstruction using audio-visual sensors," in *Proceedings - 2017 International Conference on 3D Vision, 3DV 2017*, Oct. 2018, pp. 621–629, doi: 10.1109/3DV.2017.00076.
- [28] W.Y. Yan, A. Shaker and N. El-Ashmawy, "Urban land cover classification using airborne LiDAR data: A review," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 158, pp. 295-310, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2014.11.001.
- [29] S. C. Yang and Y. C. Fan, "3D building scene reconstruction based on 3D LiDAR point cloud," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics - Taiwan, ICCE-TW 2017*, Jun. 2017, pp. 127–128, doi: 10.1109/ICCE-China.2017.7991028.
- [30] E. Ashraf, A. A. M. Khalaf, and S. M. Hassan, "Real time FPGA implementation of SAR radar reconstruction system based on adaptive OMP compressive sensing," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 185–196, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v20.i1.pp185-196.
- [31] Y. J. Ban, H. S. Kim, and C. Joon, "3D mesh reconstruction from height map and post processing," in 9th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence: ICT Convergence Powered by Smart Intelligence, ICTC 2018, Oct. 2018, pp. 1491–1493, doi: 10.1109/ICTC.2018.8539362.
- [32] T. Sugiura, A. Torii, and M. Okutomi, "3D surface reconstruction from point-and-line cloud," in Proceedings - 2015 International Conference on 3D Vision, 3DV 2015, Oct. 2015, pp. 264–272, doi: 10.1109/3DV.2015.37.

- [33] K. W. Ng, J. Abdullah, S. L. Ng, and H. L. Tong, "Snake-based boundary search for segmentation of 3D polygonal model," in *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol. 67, 2019, pp. 537–546, doi: 10.1007/978-981-13-6031-2_35.
- [34] K.-W. Ng and J. Bin Abdullah, "Slinky-based segmentation on 3D polygonal model for functional parts in computer graphics," in *International Conference on Computer Assisted Systems in Health (CASH2018)*, 2018, pp. 1–6.
- [35] S. P. Dakua, J. Abinahed, and A. Al-Ansari, "A PCA-based approach for brain aneurysm segmentation," *Multidimensional Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 257–277, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s11045-016-0464-6.
- [36] M. A. M. Fuad *et al.*, "A review on methods of identifying and counting *Aedes aegypti* larvae using image segmentation technique," *Telkomnika (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 1199–1206, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.v15i3.6422.

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